

EW, ICK: Emotional Words Investigated with Contextual Knowledge.

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Abstract

Emotions are pervasive of our everyday life and attempts to model them in more or less formal systems have flourished, from dimensional to categorical models. We face the matter adopting a frame semantics approach in order to build a knowledge graph of lexical semantic triggers reusing previously existing resources such as WordNet and VerbNet, and in particular we take as test case the concept of "Disgust", as conceptualized in Ekman's theory.

Keywords

Emotions, Commonsense Reasoning, Knowledge Representation, AI

1. Introduction

Emotions are pervasive of our everyday life, they have been recognised as an intrinsic component of socio-behavioral external world fruition, as well as being rooted in internal mental representation and appraisal dynamics, and therefore inextricably related to the human aesthetic dimension. Recently, particular attention has been given to the analysis and formalization of emotional response in respect to any kind of content which could generate some form of "engagement" (both in real life and online), generating several computational tools for emotion detection tasks to detect, measure, and identify emotional content [1]. Furthermore, emotional engagement is of primary importance in the construction of narrative and storytelling [2], [3] in a the contemporary multi-media "onlife" environment [4].

As a consequence of the complex role played by emotions in our everyday experience, attempts to elaborate satisfying computational models and methodologies have been flourishing. The two main research directions are: (i) Dimensional models: better suited to investigate inner physiological, continuous correlate of emotions [5], measured on some fixed parameters, like arousal and valence, often organized as circumplex models like Russel's [6] or Plutchick's "wheel of emotions" [7]; (ii) Categorical models: which focus more on the conscious introspection level of emotional experience, and where emotions are treated as discrete categories as in

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Ekman's Basic Emotions Theory [8], [9] based on lexical criterion, as in Shaver [10], of focused on dynamics of appraisal, as in the OCC model [11]. In social psychology, the Contempt-Anger-Disgust (CAD) triad model of moral emotions proposed by [12] relates them to specific configurations of values, termed ethics, inspired by Schweder's work [13] on morality from an anthropological perspective. The CAD triad model relates each emotion type to the violation of a specific ethic: Contempt to the Ethics of community, Anger to the Ethics of autonomy, Disgust to the Ethics of Divinity.

We propose here a frame semantics approach (cf. Section 2), considering each emotion as frame, namely, a network of relations with necessary, optional and external roles involved as participants to the realization of the semantics of the frame itself, triggered by lexical units intended as semantic pointers towards some knowledge domain. In particular in this work we are not focusing on the frame structure per se, but, starting from the Framester ontological hub as described in Section 2, in Section 3 we provide lexical coverage to one use case in particular, one of the pillars of the CAD triad: the "Disgust" frame. In Section 4 we provide example of the inferential capabilities that this formal approach can have and finally in Section 5 we envision some future works and possible developments.

2. Framester and Frame Semantics Approach

The approach adopted here to model emotions, and to connect them to their linguistic expression manifestation, reuses a formal representation of FrameNet frames [14] as formalised [15] in Framester ontological hub [16]. Ontologies in fact, namely, formal representation of some domain-knowledge, seem the perfect structure to represent the complexity of emotions as N-ary relations (frames) and to connect them to already existing semantic resources. Frames are cognitive representations of prototypical and recurrent features of events or situations. Lexical units semantically related to some scene are associated with frames, based on their schematic structure. In FrameNet, frames are also explained as *situation types*. In Framester semantics [17] observed/recalled/anticipated/imagined situations are consequently occurrences of frames. For example, representing an apparently simple situation like the moral emotion [18] "being disgusted" as a frame structure, it would require some *necessary roles* such as an agent feeling the emotion (experiencer), the emotion itself, but also some optional elements such as an emotion trigger, which could be material or immaterial, the intensity, the physiological manifestation (e.g. nausea), and some external elements such as the duration of the emotional / neurophysiological state.

Framester [16] provides a formal semantics for frames in a curated linked data version of multiple linguistic resources (e.g. besides FrameNet, WordNet [19], VerbNet [20], BabelNet [21], etc.); a cognitive layer including MetaNet [22] and ImageSchemaNet [23], connecting conceptual metaphors and image schematic sensorimotor patterns to the above-mentioned linguistic resources; factual knowledge bases (e.g. DBpedia [24], YAGO [25], etc.), and ontology schemas (e.g. DOLCE [26] [27]), with formal links between them, resulting in a strongly connected RDF/OWL knowledge graph.

Finally the FRED tool [28] is a hybrid knowledge extraction system to generate knowledge graphs directly from natural language text input. It is built with a pipeline that includes both

statistical and rule-based components, aimed at producing RDF and OWL knowledge graphs, with embedded entity linking, word-sense disambiguation, and frame/semantic role detection, aligning entities in the produced graph directly to entities from Framester resource. We use it here to test possible inferences thanks to the newly introduced Disgust frame semantic triggers.

3. Building the Disgust Frame

The pipeline to retrieve semantic triggers and organize them as knowledge graphs consists in three main steps:

1. **LU Identification:** Identify lexical units which could be related to the notion of “disgust” and evoke its conceptual frame.
2. **Querying the Resource:** Starting from these lexical units, perform a query expansion using SPARQL language to query the Framester endpoint¹ to retrieve Disgust semantic triggers.
3. **Lexical Coverage:** Build new triples to stock the knowledge about semantic triggering in RDF queryable graph format.

LU Identification As first step, lexical units concerning disgust were bootstrapped from the online version of the Ekman model².

Querying the Resource SPARQL queries³ using as variable each and any lexical unit from step 1, were used to extract semantic triggers, mainly verbs from VerbNet and synsets (sets of contextual synonyms) from WordNet.

Lexical coverage Together with semantic triggers, we introduce in the graph⁴ the property `:triggers`, pointing to another individual, `ek:Disgust`, namely the concept of Disgust, according to Ekman theory (in fact, there could be different coverage according to other emotional theories as well).

4. Evaluation

Let’s take as example a sentence like *This wave of corruption is disgusting*. Figure 1 shows the graph automatically generated with FRED tool. Thanks to the new knowledge base of semantic triggers we are able to say that `vn.data:Disgust_31010000` which is the VerbNet entry for the verb “to disgust” triggers `ek:Disgust`, namely the concept of disgust as conceptualize in Ekman’s theory. Furthermore, from the top node of the graph we can infer that the `ek:Disgust` occurrence has takes as causal role (`vn.role:Cause`) some “Wave” event, which has determiner the “Corruption”, disambiguated to WordNet synset `wn30:synset-corruptness-noun-2`.

¹Framester endpoint is available at . <http://etna.istc.cnr.it/framester2/sparql>

²Lexical units about the concept of Disgust were bootstrapped from this resource: <http://atlasofemotions.org/>

³The queries used to build the resource are available at: <https://github.com/StenDoipanni/EmoNet/blob/main/README.md>

⁴The knowledge graphs generated are available at <https://github.com/StenDoipanni/EmoNet>

Figure 1: FRED graph for *This wave of corruption is disgusting*

5. Conclusions

We presented here a first version of a lexical-coverage-for-emotion-frames-building pipeline, taking Disgust as use case, starting from the notion of “Disgust” as conceptualized and lexicalized in Ekman’s Theory. This work opens the possibility to a broad expansion to a larger lexical coverage for all Ekman’s basic emotions, and then to other emotional theories. Such a resource could allow the introduction of an emotional layer on top of pre-existing lexical resources such as FrameNet, VerbNet, WordNet etc. but also to factual knowledge bases such as DBpedia.

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